

DIVINFOOD

**Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains
to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food**

Deliverable D5.2

***Completed database GxE and final list
of SMART indexes gathering WP1-5
inputs***

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the comprehensive database developed in the DIVINFOOD project to compile all results relating to the use of agrobiodiversity in value chains, from plant breeding to the consumption of food products. Results concern the use of Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs), namely 16 types of minor cereals and legumes, used in one or more of the 9 living labs set up in the project, which covers 7 countries in Europe. This database is based on a broad approach to genotype-environment interactions (GxE), in which the environment is not limited to agro-pedo-climatic conditions and agricultural practices, but includes also the socio-economic environment. Furthermore, the results of genotype-environment interactions are addressed through a variety of benefits, defined with stakeholders, and intended to be measured and monitored over time using SMART indexes. The deliverable is structured around three sections: first, it explains the approach to GxE developed in the project, describes the search which has been done to identify a digital tool suitable for a relational database that can be fed by academic and non-academic partners, and reports the co-development of the GxE database; second, it presents the final list of the 37 SMART indexes co-defined in the work packages; third, it gathers inputs regarding the SMART indexes from data collected on NUCs use in the 9 living labs and provides an overview of the costs associated with using these NUC species and varieties.

1. Introduction

The DIVINFOOD Genotype × Environment (GxE) database is a key deliverable of the DIVINFOOD project, aimed at compiling both quantitative and qualitative data collected across the project's nine Living Labs (LLs). Its development responds to the ambition of a harmonised, interdisciplinary, and participatory data infrastructure, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs) use across diverse agro-pedo-climatic and socio-economic contexts, from seeds to finished food products.

The originality of DIVINFOOD is to broaden the analysis of genotype (G) – Environment (E) interactions in order to take in account the full agro-pedo-climatic and socio-economic context in which genotypes are used and the multiple results, including costs, that their use generates. Data on GxE and their impacts are not collected in order to statistically compare the use of the same genotype in different agro-pedo-climatic environments, as usually done in agronomy. Instead, data will reflect a wide diversity of situations in which genotypes are used, and the multiple benefits generated by their use, assessed through SMART indexes. Applied to the 16 NUCs and in the 9 LLs considered in the project, data collection will be used to highlight new business models valuing NUCs, to feed a support decision-tool for farmers and small-scale processors, and to give information about NUCs' multiple and multi-level benefits to consumers and policy-makers.

In the first part of the deliverable, we present how the database has been structured and implemented, that included, among other key issues, the selection of a suited digital tool. In the second part, we list the SMART indexes identified in DIVINFOOD work packages as relevant to assess and monitor the benefits of using NUCs. In the third part, we describe the data compiled in the database, and give an overview of the inputs related to the SMART indexes.

This deliverable has been finalised with a 6-month delay, first to benefit from the annual meeting in June 2025 to encourage partners to complete missing data and jointly verify the diversity of documented NUCs use cases, particularly with regard to the typology of NUC growers developed in Deliverable 3.1. This delay is also explained by non-anticipated staff changes at INRAE in Spring 2025, needing to find and train another person to use the database and compile the inputs on SMART indexes, that was not possible during Summer holidays. Nevertheless, all data available in the database and needed to feed other deliverables in WP1 and WP5 have been extracted and given to task members in May 2025 (due date of this deliverable) in order to avoid negative repercussions in these other work packages and ensure the success of the project. As INRAE is both the leader of the project and of this deliverable, no risk for the success of the project has been taken.

2. Development of the database

2.1 A new approach to capture Genotype-Environment interactions

In agronomy and plant breeding, the analysis of the interactions between a genotype and its environment usually only considers the biophysical environment on one hand, agronomic results, foremost yield and resistance to diseases, on other.

Then, the equation which is usually considered is the following:

$$G \times E \text{ (Be-biophysical environment)} = \text{agronomic results}$$

This equation has been enlarged by further work in agronomy, including the influence of management practices in the environment:

$$G \times E \text{ (Be-Biophysical environment} \times \text{M-management practices)} = \text{agronomic results}$$

DIVINFOOD goes beyond, by taking in account the full context in which they are used and the multiple results their use generates,

- i) by considering a wider set of environmental dimensions in which the genotype is used, to assess its performances: in addition to the biophysical environment and management practices, the technological, socio-economic and regulation environment in which the genotype is used is considered;
- ii) by considering a wider set of results, taking in account the ecosystem services (ES), the other benefits (B) and the costs (C) generated by the use of the genotype along the value chain, from plant breeding to the sale of the finished product.

The unique approach of GxE in DIVINFOOD is reflected in the following equation:

$$G \times E \text{ (Genotype} \times \text{Environment)} = \text{ES} + \text{B} + \text{C (Ecosystem Services} + \text{other Benefits} + \text{Costs)}$$

In the framework of DIVINFOOD, the component Genotype includes variety mixtures, landraces and genetically homogeneous lines (pure lines).

Moreover, the environmental component is further decomposed into:

- **Be** – Biophysical environment
- **M** – Management practices
- **T** – Processing technologies
- **Ch** – Marketing channels
- **S** – Social organisations
- **R** – Regulation

Then, the equation addressed in DIVINFOOD is as following:

$$G \times (\text{Be} \times \text{M} \times \text{T} \times \text{Ch} \times \text{S} \times \text{R}) = \text{Ecosystem Services (ES)} + \text{Other Benefits (B)} + \text{Costs (C)}$$

2.2 Nature of data

Each DIVINFOOD Work Package first contributes to collect specific data on NUC genotypes and specific components of the environment in which these genotypes are used or valued (through food products) in the LLs:

- **WP1:** Marketing Channels (Ch)
- **WP2:** Processing technologies (T)
- **WP3-4:** Biophysical environments (Be), Management practices (M)
- **WP5:** Social organisations (S), Regulations (R)

Each WP then collects data on benefits (including ecosystem services in WP3-4) and costs generated by the use of NUC genotypes in their specific environment, at the 3 main steps of the value chain:

- Agricultural product (steps “growing” and “on-farm breeding”)
- Processed product or dish (step “processing”)
- Food product or dish (step “marketing”)

Moreover, each WP completes data about the stakeholders using NUCs, who can be a farmer, a processor and/or a seller.

To assess ecosystem services and other benefits provided by the use of NUCs, DIVINFOOD favours SMART indexes (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic and Tangible), as well as simple and not expensive measurement methods as far as possible, valuing relevant simple proxies if needed, to make performance and impact assessment possible for a large number of stakeholders, and not only by researchers.

The database aims to trace complete value chains, using a digital tool capable to restructure the relationships between the agricultural product, the processed product(s) or dish(es) made from this agricultural product, and the food product(s) or dish(es) sold at the end from this agricultural product. The focus on short and mid-tier chains assumed in DIVINFOOD (maximum 2 intermediaries between the farmer and the consumer) was supposed to make this traceability easier to restructure than in longer chains.

As DIVINFOOD focuses on short and mid-tier chains, farmers are often also processors and sellers, as in the case of ‘peasant-bakers’, which is rapidly expanding in Europe. Next, to avoid stakeholder fatigue, a task force was set up between the WPs at the start of the project to avoid repeated interviews with the same stakeholder. In practical terms, the WP surveys were merged and data collectors from one WP were expected to collect data for the other WPs where possible. In addition, data collectors considered farm trials and LL meetings as opportunities to collect data. This task force was an effective organisation, but required that all questions be very clear to all data collectors.

The figure 1 represents the data flow from the work packages 1-5 to the 4 fields of the database.

Figure 1. Structure of the database on genotype use in DIVINFOOD.

2.3 Co-development of the GxE database

The GxE database was co-developed with DIVINFOOD members and stakeholders based on:

- i. **Initial specifications** (Milestone #4, December 2022, 4p) and **database conceptual modelling** into a preliminary structure (see Figure 2).
- ii. **Feedbacks from Work Package Leaders** (WP1-WP5) to align the database to the data collected in their tasks: WP1 on NUCs-based products marketing (T1.2), WP2 on processed products made with NUCs (T2.1), WP3 and WP4 on NUCs on-farm trials (T3.1, T3.2, T3.4), WP5 on social organisations and regulations framing the use of NUCs in farms and small-scale processing units (T5.3).
- iii. **Benchmark of digital tools** to identify the most adapted tool to support a relational and participatory database, and validation of the selected tool with the ExCom.
- iv. **Test of the database conceptual modelling and of the YesWiki tool** from data collected in a previous project on the use of minor cereals in short and mid-tier chains.
- v. **Final review and approval** of the GxE database and the YesWiki tool by the ExCom.

Figure 2. Conceptual model of the DIVINFOOD relational GxE database.

2.4 Selection of the digital tool

Between June and November 2023, INRAE conducted an exploratory phase aimed at identifying and testing various digital tools in order to find the best one to support the database. The objective was to find or develop a suitable open-source, participatory, and sustainable digital solution capable of managing a large, complex dataset in a collaborative context, and enabling to follow the use of the genotypes from the growing stage to the marketing stage.

The evaluation of several digital tools focused on the following criteria, aligned with FAIR data principles and the Horizon 2020 framework:

- **Relational database model**, with an ability to interlink records and trace NUCs use throughout the value chain;
- **Open-source licensing**, compliance with Open-Source initiative criteria, including free redistribution, open access to source code and support for derivative works.
- **Low cost**, preference for affordable or free solutions
- **Multi-user and user-friendly access**, with a capacity to support multiple contributors (project partners or crowdsourcing by citizens, not experts of digital tools), with features such as user registration or direct form access;
- **Mixed data**: quantitative and qualitative data
- **Data persistence**: ability to pre-load data and perform repeated entries on the same entities over time;
- **Low-code**: no requirement for development in Python, SQL, or no-code environments;
- **Storage capacity**: ability to manage up a high quantity of data;
- **Rapid deployment**: tool should be readily available without requiring external IT services or extensive training;
- **Data residency**: data should be hosted within the EU, in accordance with data sovereignty and GDPR considerations;

- **Sustainability:** the database must remain accessible for at least 10 years following the end of the project.

This exploratory phase enabled INRAE to refine the technical specifications for the database and shortlist appropriate tools for the subsequent implementation phase. During this phase, INRAE tested and self-trained on five candidate tools.

In June 2023, INRAE participated in a seminar on crowd-sourcing tools, with the aim of identifying experts able to recommend tools aligned with the project's database requirements. Despite these efforts, no immediately suitable solution was proposed by the organisers.

In parallel, INRAE carried out an extensive online search, including the use of AI tools such as ChatGPT, which identified 12 potential database tools. Additionally, an INRAE's *'Digital Project Officer'* was also consulted, although they were ultimately unable to propose a workable solution. Additional technical consultation was carried out with a computer scientist regarding data formats and the use of BaseRow, who assisted with prospecting and the practical application of BaseRow for data recording tests. However, they did not lead to a viable long-term solution.

Following this preliminary phase, five tools were selected for in-depth testing and assessment:

- **OpenDataKit** is a free and open-source tool designed for data collection in agricultural fields, it is primarily optimized for mobile survey workflows and lacks robust relational data modeling features. Although it supports offline data entry and repeated submissions, it is less suited to managing interconnected records across multiple tables — such as tracing products or entities through a supply chain. Additionally, hosting within the EU to ensure GDPR compliance requires self-managed infrastructure, which may pose challenges for rapid deployment and long-term sustainability.
- **BaseRow** is a modern, user-friendly platform that supports relational data models and low-code customization. However, it operates under a dual licensing model, with advanced features and hosted services tied to a commercial offering. While a self-hosted open-source version exists, deploying and maintaining it securely within the EU requires additional technical resources. Moreover, questions remain around its long-term roadmap and sustainability as a relatively young product. These factors introduce risk for a public or multi-stakeholder European project where predictability, independence, and data sovereignty are key considerations.
- **Airtable** is widely praised for its intuitive interface and robust collaborative features, but it is a proprietary, cloud-based solution hosted by a US-based company. This poses significant challenges for projects governed by European data protection regulations, as its default hosting does not guarantee GDPR compliance or data residency within the EU. Additionally, Airtable's long-term sustainability is vendor-dependent, with usage costs scaling quickly based on user numbers and storage needs. The lack of open-source availability also limits the ability to adapt or self-host the tool beyond the duration of the project.
- **Orchestra**, although promising as a collaborative and community-driven platform, remains a niche with limited public documentation and a smaller user base. The setup often requires technical configuration and may not offer out-of-the-box functionality for structured data management or long-term data persistence. Its open-source status and hosting options are not always clearly documented, which raises concerns regarding data residency, GDPR alignment, and the ability to guarantee access and support over a 10+

year project lifecycle. As such, it lacks the maturity and operational clarity needed for a Europe-wide deployment.

- **YesWiki** is a self-hostable platform developed and maintained within the EU. It supports full compliance with GDPR and European data sovereignty principles. YesWiki enables collaborative, multi-user data entry and accommodates both qualitative and quantitative information through customisable forms. While it is not a relational database in the traditional sense, its flexibility and adaptability make it particularly suitable for participatory, community-driven knowledge management. It makes an ideal choice for participatory, decentralized projects focused on documentation, traceability, and inclusivity over the long term. It also supports data export in multiple formats, including CSV, JSON, RSS feed, and embeddable widgets, ensuring ease of reuse and interoperability.

Then, after a comprehensive evaluation of the 5 tools, YesWiki stand out as the most appropriate solution for managing the project's database in a European context. Although OpenDataKit is free and open-source, it is primarily designed for linear, form-based data collection and presents significant limitations when it comes to modifying or updating repeated entries over time—a critical need for longitudinal tracking or supply chain analysis. BaseRow and Airtable both offer modern interfaces and relational features, but they are private platforms, with key functionalities and data capacity locked behind paid tiers. Neither tool is fully open-source, and their default hosting arrangements fall outside the EU, raising serious concerns around data residency and GDPR compliance. Orchestra requires substantial setup time and technical configuration, and the hidden costs in terms of staff time and long-term maintenance pose a barrier for projects with limited resources or tight timelines. YesWiki has been selected to support the **DIVINFOOD database for its alignment with key project requirements as transparency, collaboration and long-term data accessibility, including a fully open-source licensing, cost-effectiveness, and long-term sustainability.**

The table 1 summarises the tool evaluation along the project’s criteria.

NB. The Microsoft well-known tool for relational databases, Access, has not been considered as several DIVINFOOD members did not have Microsoft licences, and because this tool is difficult to use.

Table 1. Evaluation of digital tools to support the DIVINFOOD relational database.

Criterion	Open Data Kit	AirTable	BaseRow	Orchestra	YesWiki
<i>Relational data model</i>	☒ Limited, via IDs	☑ Yes. Native links between tables	☑ Yes. Relational model	☑ Yes. Relational Structure	⚠ Hyperlink-based, not relational
<i>Open-source licensing</i>	☑ Yes. Fully open-source	☒ No, Proprietary software	☒ No, proprietary, partial free tier	☒ Private	☑ Yes (GPL open-source)
<i>Cost</i>	☑ Free	☒ \$24 per collaborator/ per month billed monthly or \$20 per	☒ \$10 per user/month billed yearly. \$12 billed monthly	☒ €€ Unknown	⚠ Free or 3,200€ for training

		collaborator/ per month billed annually			
Multi-user access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes. Shared forms	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes. Multi-Collaborator	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes. User permission	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes. Software	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes. User registration possible
Data persistence/multi-entry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Low code	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Form based	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Require set up - configuration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Storage capacity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 10 K records monthly submission	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 50 000 records per base	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 50 000 records per base	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Depends on hosting
Type of data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Forms + media + text	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Text + numbers + files	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rich fields supported	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Depends on configuration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Text/media friendly
Rapid deployment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Database officer to create or sub-contracting CATA GEDEOP ?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2-3 sem. To set up. Requires initial set up	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes. Requires manual installation
Data residency	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Depends on hosting (France)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> US based by default	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Netherlands	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Can be hosted in France	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self-hosting in EU possible
Sustainability	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self-hostable, long term	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Depends on vendor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Uncertain long-term roadmap	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Open-source, long term accessible

The figure 3 summarises the work phases of the database design.

Figure 3. Work phases from April 2023 to January 2024 to design the relational database.

2.5 Database structure

Between November 2023 and January 2024, the database has been developed using YesWiki, based on available documentation and online guides.

The DIVINFOOD database is the first use of the YesWiki tool to develop a relational database. YesWiki is usually used to develop websites but its functionality was theoretically adapted to the development of a relational database. This innovative use of the tool interested a lot the European YesWiki user community, to which INRAE presented the DIVINFOOD database.

The database includes a homepage (See Figure 4), nine Living Lab-specific spaces in English (See figure 5), 4 sections with several sub-sections (see figures 6, 7, 8, 9), data summary pages for each Lab, and a forum section addressing key questions raised by DIVINFOOD project stakeholders (See figure 10).

Figure 4. Homepage of the GxE database on YesWiki.

Figure 5. Example of one Living Lab (LL Bean-Lyon) space, with the four forms, 2 resources to localise the use of the NUCs in Europe (Location and Biogeographical region of Europe), and an access to the Living Lab's data visualisation.

Add an entry : 1 - Stakeholder

1. Stakeholder name *
1. Stakeholder name

2. Stakeholder ID ⓘ *
LAST NAME - NAME - N°

3. Stakeholder activity profile ⓘ *
Choose..

For location, Select the suitable stakeholder location according to the latest version of "Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics: NUT3 – 2021 classification" Excel document **on the following link**, or to page 4 in the "Criteria to fill in - Details" on the Homepage of the GxE Divinfood Database website.

4. Location *
Choose..

5. Country ⓘ *
Choose..

6. NUC(s) name *

<input type="checkbox"/> Blue lupine (<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Faba bean (<i>Vicia faba</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Lingot bean (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>)
<input type="checkbox"/> Chickpea (<i>Cicer arietinum</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Meat bean (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>)
<input type="checkbox"/> Common bean (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Grey pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i> subsp. <i>arvense</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pea (<i>Pisum sativum</i>)
<input type="checkbox"/> Cowpea (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Lentils (<i>Lens culinaris</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Rivet wheat (<i>Triticum turgidum</i>)
<input type="checkbox"/> Einkorn (<i>Triticum monococcum</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Lima bean (<i>Phaseolus lunatas</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> White lupine (<i>Lupinus albus</i>)
<input type="checkbox"/> Emmer (<i>Triticum dicoccum</i>)		

Growing Processing Selling Submit

2. Processing >

Figure 6. Stakeholder section, dedicated to record data on genotype users (sub-sections = growing, processing, selling, to be completed depending on the activities of the stakeholder).

Add an entry : 2 – Agricultural Product

NB. An agricultural product corresponds to a specific batch from a specific plot of land, a specific variety and specific agricultural practices.

1. Agricultural product ID ⓘ *
 NUC_batch_grower_name_yyyy

2. Grower name *
 Choose..

If the stakeholder's name does not appear in this list, please create a Stakeholder file [on the following link](#)

Genotype Biophysical environment Management Practices Pre-processing and Storage Marketing Channels Benefits
 Growing and Harvest Costs Pre-processing and Storage Costs

3. NUC name *
 Choose..

4. NUC cultivar name ⓘ
 4. NUC cultivar name

5. Cultivar type

<input type="checkbox"/> DUS variety	<input type="checkbox"/> Heterogeneous Material (Population)	<input type="checkbox"/> Stakeholder doesn't know
<input type="checkbox"/> Landrace	<input type="checkbox"/> Heirloom variety	<input type="checkbox"/> Editor doesn't know
<input type="checkbox"/> Amateur variety	<input type="checkbox"/> Other type	

6. Registered in the country's official seed catalogue

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Stakeholder doesn't know
<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Editor doesn't know

7. Seed type

<input type="checkbox"/> Uncertified organic seed	<input type="checkbox"/> Certified untreated	<input type="checkbox"/> Editor doesn't know
<input type="checkbox"/> Certified conventional seed	<input type="checkbox"/> Other seed type	
<input type="checkbox"/> Certified organic seed	<input type="checkbox"/> Stakeholder doesn't know	

8. Seed source

<input type="checkbox"/> Own production	<input type="checkbox"/> Purchased from cooperative	<input type="checkbox"/> Stakeholder doesn't know
<input type="checkbox"/> Exchanged farm seed	<input type="checkbox"/> Purchased from company	<input type="checkbox"/> Editor doesn't know
<input type="checkbox"/> Purchased farm seed	<input type="checkbox"/> Other seed source	

2. Biophysical environment >

Submit Cancel

Figure 7. Agricultural Product section (sub-sections = Biophysical environment, management practices, pre-processing and storage, marketing channels, benefits, growing and harvest costs, pre-processing and storage costs).

Add an entry : 3 – Processed product / Dish

NB. The marketing of processed products or dishes is documented on another form ('food product' or 'dish'). In this form, only the processing step, and their benefits/costs, are described.

1. Processed product / Dish ID ⓘ *
 NUC_product/dish_type_processor_name_number_date

2. Processor name *
 Choose..

If the stakeholder's name does not appear in this list, please create a Stakeholder file [on the following link](#) .

3. Grower name ⓘ
 Choose..

4. Batch NUC Agricultural Product ID from which the processed product/ dish has been made
 Choose..

5. NUC Processed Product/ Dish ID (if the processed product/ dish added above has been made from another processed product) ⓘ
 Choose..

If the NUC batch or processed product ID does not appear in this list, please add an **Agricultural Product file** or a **Processed Product / Dish file** .

6. NUC name *
 Choose..

7. Food product or dish *
 Food product
 Dish

Processed Product or Dish Processing Techniques Quality Supplier Origin Benefits Costs

8. Category of agricultural product, primary processing product or processed product made in the unit by the stakeholder
 Choose..

11. Description of the processed product or dish ⓘ

12. Composition of the processed product or dish ⓘ

2. Processing Techniques >

Submit Cancel

Figure 8. Processed Product or Dish section (sub-sections = processing techniques, quality, supplier – of the raw material -, origin – of the raw material -, costs).

Add an entry : 4 – Food product / Dish

NB. Fill in one form per seller, who can use several marketing channels

1. Food Product / Dish ID *
 NUC_type of product/dish_seller name_number_date

2. Seller name *
 Choose..

If the stakeholder's name does not appear in this list, please create a Stakeholder file [on the following link](#)

3. Grower name (if not the seller)
 Choose..

4. Processor name (if not the seller and if relevant)
 Choose..

If the NUC batch or processed product ID does not appear in this list, please add an [Agricultural Product file](#) or a [Processed Product / Dish file](#) .

5. Agricultural Product ID
 Choose..

6. Processed Product / Dish ID
 Choose..

7. NUC name *
 Choose..

8. Food product or Dish ?
 Choose..

Product Description	Product Marketing Channels	Dish Description	Dish Marketing Channels	Supplier	Origin	Benefits
Costs						

2. Product Marketing Channels >

Submit Cancel

Figure 9. Food product or Dish section (sub-sections = product marketing channels, dish description, dish marketing channels, supplier – of the processed product -, origin – of the processed product -, benefits – to sell food the product or dish, costs – to sell the food product or dish -).

Questions & Answers : GXE Database

- What informations do we have to enter in the database ?**

The aim of the Genotype x Environment database is to capitalise on the data produced in the various work packages and dedicated tasks (all tasks where it is written "SMART indexes and empirical data").

We have no statistical ambitions, the aim is to trace the path of NUC-based products, from seed to shop, in around twenty diversified cases per crop (certainly less in the Nordic LLs as you address many crops).

For each stage, we need to collect data on who does what, how, with which costs and benefits, both quantitatively and qualitatively. All the questionnaires supporting the database are available, and quite short for each step (growing, processing, selling). The data will be used primarily to help farmers and processors decide whether to grow, process and sell NUC-based products.
- Shall we do the registration for one organisation or the LL should have one account on Yes Wiki?**

You can register for yourself with one account. There's no limit to the number of people who can register and change information.
- Are you focused on farms at this stage? I am not sure at the moment how we can participate in this activity.**

We are looking at the whole food supply chain of NUCs. The aim is to look at the global perspective of NUCs to understand and analyse the different food value chains. As we are working on the food supply chain, sellers and processors, who are not necessarily included in some tasks, also need to be interviewed.

Figure 10. GxE Database forum on the most common questions asked by DIVINFOOD data collectors.

2.6 Training of DIVINFOOD members

YesWiki is adapted to non-experts of digital tools, while being secured. The interface is user-friendly, it allows contributors to modify saved entries by simply reopening the page, while offering restricted control over access and editing rights. Each user must log in with a personal username to contribute, and access to sensitive data (e.g., GDPR-related content) is restricted through form-level permissions. For each field, visibility and write access can be defined depending on the LL. Forms or entire datasets can be hidden or made editable only by designated groups, ensuring a balance between openness and control.

Throughout 2024, training efforts were made to ensure all DIVINFOOD members could understand and use the tool. A first Living Lab test and feedback session was held in April 2024, followed by a broader presentation during the 2nd Annual Meeting in Copenhagen (June 2024), where four interactive practical workshops were conducted. During these sessions, LL members were introduced to key functions of the database: creating an account, navigating through their LL's pages, and using the forms to record data.

To support adoption and resolve technical issues, a weekly "Zoom clinic session" was organised and several bugs were fixed based on user feedback. However, feedback highlighted the varying levels of engagement and the perceived complexity of the forms. In response, INRAE adapted its approach: presentations were tailored to specific types of stakeholders in the food chain and to each Living Lab's context, including descriptions of which data were expected from whom.

A PowerPoint presentation was developed to introduce the YesWiki tool and explain the nature of the data to be entered (see Appendix 1). This presentation was used in training sessions and Living Lab meetings.

2.7 Supporting and coordinating the production of FAIR and quality data across Work Packages and Livings Labs

The Genotype x Environment database was designed to register the diverse data generated by DIVINFOOD members across the Living Labs (LLs), including those carrying out workshops, tasting sessions, on-farm trials, interviews, and other activities.

The figure 11 specifies the data generated by the work packages 1 to 5.

Figure 11. Data flows from WPs to the database.

With regard to data collection, INRAE supported DIVINFOOD non-expert members to conduct surveys, stressing the need to use GDPR-compliant consent forms for farmers, and to record interviews in order to transcript discourses and qualitative data. INRAE also provided several survey templates in English. These templates facilitated semi-structured interviews, handwritten note-taking and structured follow-up.

To ensure coherence across tasks, INRAE worked with task leaders to retrieve data from WP1-5. All collected surveys were compared and merged in Microsoft Excel to identify missing information and ensure consistency across WPs. A key challenge during this process was to align the different levels of analysis used to describe NUCs (whether by family, genus, species, or variety), which varied depending on the research scope of each task.

By Month 36, task members were expected to complete and consolidate missing data on the YesWiki platform, with particular attention to the costs and benefits experienced by stakeholders involved in current NUC-based food value chains. This phase also involves expanding the scope of

data collection to reflect the diversity of farm types identified in Deliverable D3.1, the variety of processing and selling initiatives observed across Living Labs and the three orientations of business models identified from the first surveys (see deliverable 5.3).

To facilitate data collection and registration in the YesWiki, INRAE prepared a 60-page user guide intended for consortium members.

3. SMART indexes reflecting the benefits of using NUCs

The database is intended to register, among other data, data related to the SMART indexes identified in the work packages through participatory activities as relevant to assess and monitor the benefits generated by the use of NUCs from farms to food shops and restaurants. Important to note, DIVINFOOD targets indexes which are easy to understand and easy to measure in order to facilitate their use by stakeholders.

The deliverables 1.4, 2.2, 3.5 and 4.3 describe the definition of the SMART indexes in the work packages W1-WP4. In the day-to-day activities of the project, the term “indicator” is finally preferred than “index” as easier to understand, and because “index” may refer to an aggregation of indicators that was not the initial ambition. WP5 was expected to define SMART indicators from the qualitative and quantitative data collected through WP1-4 surveys as well as from specific surveys on territorial arrangements around NUCs carried out in the WP5 (task 5.3).

We present below the consolidated list of SMART indicators developed across the 5 Work Packages, WP1-WP4 addressing a specific segment of biodiversity-based value chains while WP5 focusing on the benefits identified within local collective initiatives. A selection of the SMART indexes reflecting the four types of Ecosystem Services has been made within the relative long list provided by the WP3, to align with the GxE equation while keeping the objective of a realistic list to be assessed and monitored by NUCs users as far as possible. Indicators finally reflect key benefits of NUCs use such as market differentiation and consumer engagement (WP1), food quality (WP2), ecosystem services at farm level (WP3), breeding strategies supporting genetic diversity (WP4), peer and multi-actor territorial cooperation, and citizen participation (WP5). Together, they provide a comprehensive and operational framework to assess the integration and impact of neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs) across the entire value chain, and around.

WP1 - Deliverable D1.4 - Typology of short and mid-tier chains valuing biodiversity, including SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in marketing and data

1. **Market differentiation:** *indicates that sellers who value agrobiodiversity are gaining a competitive marketing advantage because they can differentiate themselves from those sellers who only offer mainstream, conventional crop-based products*
2. **Consumer loyalty:** *indicates that a loyal consumer base is being created because there is a class of consumers who actively seek out agrobiodiversity-based products*

3. **Fair prices:** *indicates that agrobiodiversity can create a fairer distribution of value for producers, intermediaries and consumers compared to products made from mainstream, conventional crops*
4. **Value chain upgrading:** *indicates that chains valuing agrobiodiversity in food environments offer producers greater opportunities to add value to their operations by diversifying their income and contributing to the local economy*
5. **Environmental activism:** *indicates that marketing agrobiodiversity enables the sellers to participate in the social movements that aim to protect the environment*

WP2: Deliverable 2.1 - SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in processing and eating, and empirical data

1. **Processing costs:** *indicates that the use of NUCs by processors reduces processing costs by favouring mild, minimal processing techniques*
2. **Acknowledgment of NUCs by consumers:** *indicates that the use of NUCs in processing promotes consumer knowledge about the plant species from which the NUCs-based product has been made*
3. **Entrepreneurship in rural areas:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes small-scale entrepreneurship in rural areas, while large-scale entrepreneurs are rather interested in major crops*
4. **Research on mild processing:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes research on mild, minimal processing as it is expected from stakeholders*
5. **Nutritional quality:** *indicated that the use of NUCs enables processors to offer and consumers to access food products of high nutritional quality*
6. **Digestibility:** *indicates that the use of NUCs enable processors to offer and consumers to access food products of high digestibility*

WP3: Deliverable 3.5 - SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use benefits in farming, and empirical data, focus on Ecosystem services

Provisioning services

1. **Protein content in yield:** *indicates that NUCs grains have an adequate protein content*
2. **Stability of yield:** *indicates that NUCs' yields are stable due to the rusticity of the crops*
3. **By-products:** *indicates that NUCs are a source of valuable by-products (e.g., straw appreciated by animals)*
4. **Number of cultivated NUC species/varieties** at farm level within a calendar year: *indicates that farms growing NUCs promote a wide diversity of minor species/varieties*

Regulating services

5. **Pollinator attractiveness:** *indicates that growing NUCs is attractive for pollinators*
6. **Level of natural pest and disease resistance of NUC/main crop:** *indicates that NUCs are naturally more resistant to pests and diseases than major crops*
7. **Soil cover capacity:** *indicates that NUCs have a competitive ability against weeds and thus promote a reduction in chemical weed control*

Supporting services

8. **Fertiliser use:** *indicates that growing NUCs promotes a reduction in fertiliser use*
9. **Plant residues and nutrients from previous year on cropland:** *indicates that growing NUCs provides nutrients for subsequent crops*
10. **Soil cover duration:** *indicates that NUCs growing allows the soil to be covered for a significant period of the year*
11. **Soil quality:** *indicates that NUCs growing contributes to maintain or increase soil quality*

Cultural services

12. **Recreation:** *indicates that growing NUCs promotes recreation events*
13. **Aesthetic value:** *indicates that using NUCs in farms contributes to a more attractive (non-monotonous) landscape*
14. **Cultural significance:** *indicates that using NUCs in farms promotes local heritage*

Other benefits

15. **Income for the farmer:** *indicates that the cultivation of NUCs is a source of income for the farmer, both directly and indirectly (e.g., through recreation events or by-products)*

WP4: Deliverable 4.3 - SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in breeding, and empirical data

1. **Agroecological breeding environment:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes the development of agroecological breeding target environment that promotes the selection of resilient and robust varieties*
2. **Genetic diversity within cultivars:** *indicates that the use of NUCs favours the cultivation of genetically heterogeneous cultivars (adapted landraces, open pollinated varieties, populations, organic heterogeneous material and organic varieties)*
3. **Added-value target traits:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes the consideration of a plurality of traits, especially “added-value” traits beside productivity: food Quality and taste traits, food processing related traits*
4. **Multi-actor involvement:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes the involvement of farmers and other actors of the value chain in cultivar development*
5. **Genetic resources mobilisation:** *indicates that the use of NUCs enables farmers and breeders to mobilise genetic resources from in situ and ex situ conservation*
6. **Small and medium scale entrepreneurship in the breeding and seed sectors in the rural areas:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes the development of smaller scale enterprises counter-balancing the very strong market concentration of the breeding and seed sector.*
7. **Farmer capacity building in breeding:** *indicates that the use of NUCs in (participatory) breeding is supposed to enable interested farmers to breed by themselves*
8. **Citizen awareness on agrobiodiversity benefits:** *indicates that the use of NUCs in (participatory) breeding is supposed to increase citizen awareness of agrobiodiversity benefits*

WP5: Deliverable 5.5 on governance arrangements (in progress, due date M60)

1. **Cooperation between peers:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes collaboration between peers to face the lack of agronomic references and share resources*
2. **Multi-actor cooperation:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes multi-actor cooperation to build the NUCs’ reputation and markets*
3. **Citizen participation:** *indicates that the use of NUCs promotes the participation of citizens to the development of NUCs seeds, products and markets*

4. Results

4.1 Metadata

Twenty-nine members of DIVINFOOD registered data in the database, reflecting the success of its participatory ambition and user-friendly conception.

The database contained **512** entries in September 2025, including 117 agricultural products, 139 processed products and 86 food products and dishes.

On average, each Living Lab contributed with 57 entries.

Table 2 summarises stakeholder distribution and product types across the 9 Living Labs. Each LL focuses on 3 different categories: agricultural products, processed products, and food products/dishes.

In total, 170 stakeholders were registered in September 2025 in the database, with the majority being farmers (55) and farmer-processor-sellers (42), reflecting the emphasis placed in DIVINFOOD on short food supply chains.

The farmer-related categories (farmer, farmer-processor-seller, farmer-seller) account for 70% of the total of stakeholders, among whom stakeholders who are only farmers represent 32%.

Processors include small and medium-size food companies, individual and collective restaurants. Sellers are also diverse, including specialised food shops and online platforms.

Looking at LLs, the LL CerOcc has the highest number of stakeholders (50) and total products (108), while the LL Meat Bean Lyon has the most diverse stakeholder mix, with a significant representation of processor-sellers (6) and sellers (4).

The LL Leg ItSwitz and LL CerHung are the only two Living Labs with a number of stakeholder below 10, 7 and 6 respectively.

Product-wise, agricultural products (117) and processed products (139) are more represented than food products/dishes (86) but without a too significant imbalance, reflecting the ambition of the project to cover the entire supply chain.

Nevertheless, data distribution highlights the lack of experience of some partners in investigating sellers, as well as the difficulty to follow genotypes from farms to food shops or restaurants, especially in mid-tier chains.

Table 2. Number of stakeholders and products registered in the GxE DIVINFOOD database in October 2025, according to LLs and categories (*F: Farmer, FPS: Farmer-Processor-Seller, FS: Farmer-Seller, P: Processor; PS: Processor-Seller, S: Seller. In brackets, number of NUC species for the concerned LL*)

Living Labs	F	FPS	FS	P	PS	S	Other	Total of Stakeholders	Agricultural Products	Processed products	Food Products	Total of products
LL1 – Bean Lyon	3	5	5	0	6	4	1	24	14 (1)	12	30	80
LL2 – Bean Cast	8	1	1	1	2	0	0	13	9 (1)	9	4	35
LL3 - Cer Occ	11	27	4	0	2	4	2	50	47 (2)	33	28	158
LL4 – Leg ItSwitz	1	4	0	1	1	0	0	7	5 (1)	27	0	39
LL5 - Gpea Port	2	0	3	1	4	0	0	10	7 (1)	13	7	37
LL6 - Faba Nord	6	0	1	1	2	3	0	13	6 (1)	2	3	24
LL7 - Leg Nord	11	1	3	0	2	7	0	24	18 (3)	12	8	62
LL8 – Leg Hung	12	1	5	0	3	2	0	23	4 (3)	10	6	43
LL9 - Cer Hung	1	3	0	0	2	0	0	6	7 (2)	21	0	34
TOTAL	55	42	22	4	24	20	3	170	117	139	86	512

The distribution of surveyed stakeholders in each LL reflects the diversity of local actors included in the database (figure 12), even if farmers who grow, process and sell NUCs are a key profile, in line with the emphasis placed in DIVINFOOD on short food chains, for which there are knowledge gaps.

Figure 12. Distribution of surveyed stakeholders in each LL.

This database offers the advantage of compiling a large amount of data, allowing a product to be potentially tracked from raw material production to marketing. The amount of registered data varies depending on the living lab and can also be considered an indirect indicator of the momentum built around NUCs in each region and the enthusiasm they generate.

4.2 Overview of use cases (G and E)

Table 3 provides a comprehensive overview of the farm environments and key stakeholder characteristics registered in the database across the nine LLs of DIVINFOOD in Europe. These LLs, located in France, Italy, Switzerland, Portugal, Denmark, Sweden and Hungary, represent a diverse and valuable cross-section of European agricultural landscapes. The data reveals significant variations in climatic conditions, farm structures, and operational profiles among the different labs.

A first difference between the LLs concerns organic farming practices. Data shows a total of 76 organic farms out of the 119 involved across all LLs. However, this commitment is not uniform: LL3 (CerOcc, France) stands out as a leader, with 37 of its 42 farms (approximately 79%) being organic. Similarly, LL6 (FabaNord, Atlantic region) and LL1 (BeanLyon, France) show high organic engagement with 6 out of 7 and 11 out of 13 farms, respectively. In stark contrast, LL2 (BeanCast, France) and LL5 (GpeaPort, Mediterranean) report no organic farms among their producers, indicating varying agricultural priorities and practices across the network.

This diversity is further increased by the distinct biogeographical regions and climatic conditions. The LLs are situated in Alpine, Continental, Mediterranean, Atlantic, and Pannonian regions. This geographical spread is directly reflected in the annual precipitation data: LLs experience very different conditions. Farms of the LL1, located in the Alpine and Continental region, receive the

highest precipitation at 950 mm, which is over 27% more than the network average. On the other end of the spectrum, farms of the LL9 (CerHung, Pannonian region) operates in a much drier environment with only 468 mm of rain, approximately 37% less than the average. Mediterranean and continental sites (LL2–LL7) fall mostly in the 700–850 mm range. This suggests a strong climatic gradient from cool-wet alpine regions to warm-dry continental plains.

Regarding farm characteristics, Table 3 highlights three key metrics: total farm surface, farm surface for NUCs, and the number of cultivated species. The utilised agricultural area per farm varies dramatically within and between landscape locations: from 0.02 ha to 580 ha. LL7 (LegNord, Continental/Atlantic) and LL6 (FabaNord) consist of very large farms, with mean surfaces around 177 and 323 ha, respectively. LL7 shows the widest range (26–580 ha), indicating a high diversity of selected farms. Conversely, LL5 and LL1 are composed of much smaller farms, ranging [0.03- 10] and [0.07- 80] ha.

The portion of surface cultivated with NUC species also varies significantly. On average it represents more than 6% of the UAA. But this average masks a great deal of variability. Highest percentage occur in LL5 (40%) and LL6 (15.5%), while the lowest are in LL1 and LL2.

An indicator of the farm “Agrobiodiversity” can be the number of cultivated species seen as the species richness. LL1 is a clear outlier, with on average 42.5 different species cultivated per farm, over 2.5 times the network average of 16.5 species. The lowest values are found in LL2, and LL5, with averages of 7.3 and 3.8 species / farm, suggesting a more specialised production model.

Finally, the economic data, represented by the average seller turnover, are sparse. Where available (LL1, LL3), values range from 14k€ to over 1,300 k€ with very high means and extremely large standard deviations. The calculated average for the two labs (LL1 and LL3) which provided information, is approximately 415k€, but the absence of data from the other seven LLs prevents a meaningful economic comparison across the entire network.

In summary, the data sample describes a strong ecological gradient and appears to represent European biogeographical regions quite well.

Alpine and continental sites, wetter, tend to host high species richness (LL1, LL8), with high variability in farm size. Mediterranean sites (LL2, LL4, LL5) seems more fragmented, drier, and show lower NUC area and species richness. Atlantic and continental-Atlantic landscapes (LL6, LL7) have large UAA surfaces and high NUC values, pointing to structurally rich environments. Pannonian sites (LL9) appear dry with intermediate structural metrics, but lack species.

Table 3 effectively illustrates that the DIVINFOOD LLs constitute a diverse European network. Stakeholders operate under different environmental conditions, manage farms that vary greatly in scale and structure, and implement varying levels of crop diversity and organic practices. This diversity makes the network a powerful tool for understanding minor legume and cereal systems across the multifaceted agricultural landscape of Europe.

Table 3. Characterisation of the nine European LLs within the DIVINFOOD project: farm environments and stakeholder profiles

Living Labs	Farm environments			Stakeholders			
	Number of organic farms/total farms	Biogeographical region	Annual precipitations (mm; mean \pm s.d.)	Utilized agricultural area (UAA) in ha; [min-max] mean \pm s.d.	NUCs UAA in ha; [min-max] mean \pm s.d. (% of total UAA)	Farm number of cultivated species (mean \pm s.d.)	Seller: [min-Max] of turnover k€/year (mean \pm s.d.)
LL1 – Bean Lyon	11/13	Alpine and continental	950 \pm 287	[0.07-80] 10.6 \pm 22.5	[0.0003 - 0.1] 0.02 \pm 0.04 0.2%	42.5 \pm 16.4	[14-1300] 292 \pm 421
LL2 – Bean Cast	0/10	Mediterranean and atlantic	762 \pm 240	[0.02-100] 41.2 \pm 49.3	[0.0004 - 3] 0.8 \pm 1.5 1.9%	7.3 \pm 5.7	No data
LL3 - Cer Occ	37/42	Mediterranean, continental and atlantic	818 \pm 246	[0.3-430] 79.9 \pm 74.5	[0.0007 - 35] 8.4 \pm 9.9 10.5%	9.7 \pm 6.6	[100-1100] (538 \pm 415)
LL4 – Leg ItSwitz	2/5	Mediterranean	738 \pm 99	[0.1-28] 17.5 \pm 9.9	[0.05-2.2] 0.7 \pm 1.0 3.8%	14 (single data)	No data
LL5 - Gpea Port	0/5	Mediterranean	845 \pm 80	[0.03-10] 5.5 \pm 4.1	[0.7- 4] 2.2 \pm 2.2 40%	3.8 \pm 3.8	No data
LL6 - Faba Nord	6/7	Atlantic	690 \pm 92	[26-320] 177.2 \pm 127.4	[15-30] 27.5 \pm 15.2 15.5%	12.5 \pm 18.4	No data
LL7 - Leg Nord	12/15	Continental and atlantic	739 \pm 127	[26-580] 323.2 \pm 223.0	[0.01-50] 8.2 \pm 14.7 2.5%	14.4 \pm 19.9	No data
LL8 – Leg Hung	5/18	Continental and panonnian	690 \pm 123	[0.15-160] 20.8 \pm 42.3	[1.1-2.5] 1.7 \pm 0.7 8.0%	28.1 \pm 16.3	No data
LL9 - Cer Hung	3/4	Panonnian	468 \pm 65	[53-300] 138.3 \pm 140.1	[0.7-7.5] 3.3 \pm 2.9 2.4%	No data	No data
TOT/AVG	TOT: 76/119	TOT: Alpine, continental, Mediterranean, atlantic and panonnian	AVG: 744 \pm 132	TOT: [0.02-580] 90.5 \pm 106.2	TOT: [0.000 3- 50] 6.0 \pm 8.6 6.6%	AVG: 16.5 \pm 12.7	TOT: [14-1300] 415 \pm 174

4.3 Case studies on GxE

4.3.1 Same G in different E

First case: Stakeholder A vs. stakeholder B (LL Bean Lyon)

Stakeholder A grows meat bean, haricot viande landrace, in a clayey, neutral pH soil. The fertility is medium and the farm is organic labelled and is located at 980m (medium mountain), in a very rainy environment. She mentions the following benefits: 1- good variety because it's climbing 2- very resistant to diseases and pests

Stakeholder B grows meat bean, haricot viande landrace, in a silty clayey, with basic pH soil. The fertility is high and the farm is organic labelled and is located at 300m (valley). She mentions the following benefits: 1- good disease resistance 2- good yield 3- fast production 4- easy dehulling

Then, benefits are partially shared (good disease resistance) between the 2 growers who both cultivate the G “haricot viande” and who are located in different E. The other benefits reported are different.

Second case: Stakeholder C vs. Stakeholder D (LL Cer Occ, einkorn)

Stakeholder C grows einkorn, IGP de Haute Provence variety, in a clayey and low fertile soil, in the plain, with organic certification. He also processes einkorn grains for flour production, which he sells directly. He mentions the following benefits: 1- rustic cultivar 2- few problems 3- resistant to disease (more than selected varieties) 4- long vegetation period

Stakeholder D grows einkorn, IGP de Haute Provence variety, at 138m height. He also processes einkorn grains, but for bread production, which he sells directly. He mentions the following benefits: 1- yield stability 2- nutrient cereal variety

Then, benefits are partially shared for the same G in the two different E: both stakeholders report how this variety is rustic, since its yield is stable. However, stakeholder C points more the attention on the benefit “length of the vegetation period”, while stakeholder D highlights the high nutritional value.

4.3.2 Same E, different G

First case: Stakeholder E vs stakeholder F (LL LegItSwitz, white lupine)

Stakeholder E grows white lupine Italian landrace “Dolce di Maremma”, in a sandy, neutral and low fertile soil, in the plain. He mentions the following benefits: 1- no input use 2- benefits for pollinators and soil 3- benefits for consumer health.

Stakeholder F grows white lupine, a Chilean variety, in a sandy neutral medium-low fertile soil, in the plain-valley. He mentions the following benefits: 1- high disease resistance 2- benefits for pollinators.

Benefits are partially shared, both of them report benefits for pollinators, but E also reports benefits for the soil and the consumers and no input use, while F highlights the high disease

resistance of his Chilean variety. They are located in similar environment but they cultivate different genotypes.

Second case: Stakeholder H vs stakeholder K (LL CerHung, einkorn)

Stakeholder H grows einkorn landrace “GT-2139”, in an organic farm with clayey and low fertile soil, in the plain, in a dry and with low precipitations environment. She mentions only the following benefit: 1-crop diversification.

Stakeholder K grows einkorn landrace “Bözödi”, in an organic farm with sandy and low fertile soil, in the plain, in a dry and with low precipitations environment, with heat waves. He mentions the following benefits: 1-crop diversification 2-more resistant than common wheat.

Benefits are partially shared as both of them report the benefit “crop diversification”. Stakeholder K also reports a higher resistance compared to common wheat. The two growers share similar environments (low fertility, plain, dry and low precipitations), but cultivate different genotypes of einkorn.

4.4 Overview of G chains

It has been much more difficult than expected to retrace food value chains from G to food products, although DIVINFOOD places the emphasis on short and mid-tier chains. The case of farmer-processor-seller (n=42) was the easiest to document.

For most cases, it was not possible to know how NUC raw material sold by farmers was exactly used by processors as those ones usually mix different batches of raw material.

On the other hand, sellers know who processed the product, but usually do not know which farmer(s) produced the raw material.

Nevertheless, in addition to the 42 farmers-processors-sellers, 40 multi-actor chains have been documented across the LLs, highlighting strong cooperation between farmers and restaurants and between farmers, local processors, and specialised food shops (e.g., organic stores, bakeries).

These examples will be developed in the deliverable on business models (D5.3, postponed to M46) and used in the support decision-tool (D5.4, due date M56).

4.5 Inputs related to the SMART indexes

Collected data globally confirm the relevance of the SMART indexes identified in the WPs through participatory activities.

More than 800 verbatims have been collected about the benefits of using NUCs across the value chain, and have been classified according to the SMART indexes. Appendix 2 shows a screenshot of this classification in the case of a LL.

Nevertheless, the stakeholders interviewed qualify certain benefits, indicating that they are not systematic. For example, stable yields regardless of the environment are globally confirmed for einkorn but much less so for legumes, which is also highlighted in the literature.

Analysis in labs for nutritional quality and digestibility completed the interviews.

Table 4 summarises trends in index values across the LLs. These trends little vary according to the country but index values are environment-sensitive, as illustrated in the table. Especially, our approach to GxE is adapted to capture how benefits tend to be influenced by G and E component(s): Be (Biophysical environment), M (Management practices), T (processing techniques), Ch (Marketing channels), S (Social organisations), R (Regulations). However, these trends must be considered in light of the sample surveyed, which remains small on a European scale. NUCs are still rarely used in certain regions, which makes it impossible to perform statistical analyses. This summary table is intended less as a set of benchmarks than as a basis for discussion with current and potential NUC users, consumers and policy-makers. Above all, it shows the full range of benefits that can be gained from using NUCs, which go far beyond yield or turnover.

Table 4. Inputs related to SMART indexes from the 9 LLs

Benefits of using NUCs in marketing	
Market differentiation	(++) Highlighted by stakeholders for cereals, less for legumes
Consumer loyalty	(++) Ch- and T-sensitive High in short chains, especially direct selling; consumers of cereal-based products are in search of minimal processed bread in relation with gluten concerns
Fair prices	(+/-) Ch- and M-sensitive Stakeholders highlight the difficulty to cover production costs for small quantities, especially in mid-tier chains Mechanisation of harvests is not always possible for legumes (e.g., LL Bean Lyon), generating extra costs
Value chain upgrading	(++) Ch-, G-, M- and T-sensitive NUC production promotes shorter chains as long chains prioritise major crops; value chain upgrading is easier in case of local G, organic M, and minimal T
Environmental activism	(+/-) Ch and S-sensitive Depends on the education around NUCs-based products
Benefits of using NUCs in processing and eating	
Processing costs	(-) T- and S-sensitive NUCs processing, even minimal, remains costly due to small quantities (no scale economy) Low tech equipment and peer collaboration can help reducing these costs
Consumer upskilling about NUCs	(-) Ch- and S-sensitive Depends on the communication around the product as consumers are not used to recognise plant species in their plate (see Deliverable D1.1, European survey)
Entrepreneurship	(++) G-, M- and T-sensitive NUCs processing is an opportunity for small and medium-entrepreneurs to establish and differentiate, all the more in the case of local G, organic M, and minimal T

Research on mild processing	(+/-) NUCs, especially legumes, are also studied in non-mild processing (e.g., extrusion, protein isolates) (e.g., in DIVINFOOD's sister projects)
Nutritional quality	(++) G- and T-sensitive Both stakeholders and lab analyses confirm the nutritional value of NUCs-based products, but also highlighted anti-nutritional factors that have to be controlled and reduced DIVINFOOD helps identifying varieties and processing techniques reducing these anti-nutritional factors
Digestibility	(+/-) G- and T-sensitive This benefit has been highlighted for einkorn and rivet wheat processed by stone mills due to a lower rate of gluten, and confirmed through lab analyses (Desclaux et al., 2026) This remains a barrier for consuming legumes, although certain processing techniques studied in DIVINFOOD (fermentation) increase their digestibility
Benefits of using NUCs in growing	
Protein content in grains	(++) M- and G-sensitive Legumes are typically a source of proteins. Minor cereals also offer good protein rates [11-18% in the sample] (comparable to the average rate of common wheat in Europe)
Stability of yield	(+/-) G and M-sensitive Highlighted for minor cereals, less for legumes Faba bean shows the highest yield at 3.7 t/ha, followed by blue lupin at 2.45 t/ha. Cereals like emmer and rivet wheat have moderate yields of 2.15 t/ha and 1.9 t/ha, respectively. In contrast, crops like lentil record significantly lower yields. Einkorn yield varies between the two different environment where it was cropped: in the Occitania region (France) it reached 1.5 t/ha, while in Hungary it reached 2 t/ha. Regarding minor cereals, the yield is mentioned as lower than for other main cereals (common or durum wheat) but as NUCs are growing on poor soils, farmers are satisfied concerning the yield (1-2 t/ha), mainly concerning the stability of the yield even in poor weather years where common wheat failed.
By-products	(+) G-sensitive Highlighted for cereals. Especially animals appreciate einkorn straw, and landraces tend to have a higher straw height compared with modern varieties.
Number of cultivated NUC species/varieties	(++) Ch-sensitive 20% of farmers registered in the database mix NUCs with others crops like wheat, spelt, sunflower, rapeseed, quinoa, faba bean, oats, clover, pea, etc. In rarer cases, NUCs are used in agroforestry system (e.g., grass pea or einkorn in olive trees). Farms grow around 4 to 6 species (e.g., einkorn, lentil, chickpea, lupin). 52 NUC varieties are used across the 9 LLs. Farmers in direct selling use more varieties than farmers producing raw material.
Pollinator attractiveness	(+/-) G-sensitive

	Lupin and faba bean are highlighted for attracting pollinators like bees.
Pest and disease resistance	(++) G- and M-sensitive Almost all farmers point out the ability of NUCs to resist to pests and diseases without chemical inputs. Einkorn is observed as very resistant to rust, while its outer layer protects it from disease during storage; Meat Bean and Lupin noted for requiring very few or no treatments. However, they observe differences between G and according to management practices (e.g., mix of varieties reduce the risks).
Soil cover capacity	(+/-) G- and M-sensitive Faba bean provides good weed suppression; einkorn's dense sowing helps control weeds.
Soil quality	(++) G- and M-sensitive NUC species help restore soil quality. These resilient plants can thrive where conventional crops fail, turning degraded land into productive landscapes. Einkorn for example is able to grow on poor soils, where modern wheat failed. Thanks to the NUCs, some farmers are thus bringing abandoned land back into cultivation.
Fertiliser use	(++) G-sensitive Legumes fix nitrogen in the soil, enabling farmers to reduce the use of fertilisers. Stakeholders observed variations according to G.
Plant residues and nutrients	(++) G- and M-sensitive Plant residues and nutrients play a crucial role in maintaining soil fertility. When plant residues decompose, they release essential nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium back into the soil, improving its structure and supporting healthy crop growth. Incorporating residues, as usually done by NUC growers, also enhances organic matter content, water retention, and microbial activity in the soil.
Soil cover duration	(+/-) G- and M-sensitive Farmers highlight the interest of some varieties rather than crops, e.g., "This variety (of einkorn) is of particular interest because of its earliness: I can plant it early (late September/1st October sowing), and therefore it covers the soil when heavy autumn rainfall arrives and then, maintains the soil"
Recreation	(+) Ch- and S-sensitive Highlighted for minor cereals: multiplication of bread festivals addressing the issue of local landraces and/or minimal processing
Aesthetic value	(+) G-sensitive NUCs use promote landscape diversification. Certain landraces have attractive colours (e.g., haricot-viande, see Figure 13)
Cultural significance	(++) G-sensitive NUCs use promote local landraces
Income for farmers	(+) G- and Ch-sensitive

	Meat Bean sold at €6.25–€7.95/kg; Einkorn flour sold at €7/kg versus €1.8/kg for conventional wheat flour. The farmer's income is less linked to crop yield than to the NUC user's ability to find niches for promoting and marketing his/her product, particularly by processing the harvest him/herself on farm.
Benefits of using NUCs in breeding	
Agroecological breeding environment	(++) NUCs promote agroecological breeding environment to confirm their resilience to biotic and abiotic stresses
Genetic diversity within cultivars	(++) G-sensitive Only 25% of the NUCs varieties used across the LLs are registered in the European catalogue, reflecting a wide diversity of used cultivars
Added-value target traits	(++) G- and Ch-sensitive NUCs varieties are selected for taste, nutritional quality, typicality
Multi-actor involvement	(++) G- and R-sensitive NUCs promote participatory breeding involving farmers, researchers, breeders, processors, consumers, etc.
Genetic resources mobilisation and preservation	(++) 28% of farmers grow pure lines, while 31% and 41% of them say they use landraces or populations, respectively
Small and medium scale entrepreneurship	(++) G-sensitive NUC breeding, especially landraces, is of little interest for major seed companies, opening opportunities for smaller enterprises
Farmer capacity in breeding	(++) G- and R-sensitive Farmers use NUC populations and landraces, and experience variety crossings
Citizen awareness	(+/-) S-sensitive NUC breeding remains a technical activity needing specific efforts to raise citizen awareness
Benefits of using NUCs in territories	
Peer cooperation	(++) S-sensitive Shared dehulling machines; informal seed exchanges between neighbours.
Multi-actor cooperation	(++) S- and R-sensitive NUCs use has been supported by FEADER (local development) and receives growing support within local food policies
Citizen participation	(++) G-, M-, T-, Ch- and S-sensitive Citizens are involved in landraces saving (e.g., gardeners), NUCs promotion, low tech mills restoration, and short chain development, especially in case of organic farming

Figure 13. Aesthetic value of the meat bean rehabilitated in the LL BeanLyon.

4.6 Costs associated with the use of NUCs and solutions to reduce costs to NUCs use

Surveys conducted among NUC growers and processors generated extensive data on the cost structures associated with cultivating and processing these species and varieties, as well as on effective, transferable strategies to mitigate such costs. These data will directly inform several deliverables of WP5, including: the development of innovative business models (D5.3, postponed to M46); a decision-support tool for farmers and processors considering the integration of NUCs into their operations (D5.5, M54); and a policy document synthesising targeted policy briefs for different food-chain segments, countries and regions (D5.6, M60).

Overall, producers reported relatively few production costs that diverge substantially from those of major cereals and legumes. Einkorn wheat constitutes a notable exception due to its hulled nature and the presence of a robust triple-layered outer coat characteristic of ancient wheat species. While this anatomical feature confers agronomic advantages—particularly increased resistance to biotic stress—it necessitates dehulling prior to commercialisation or processing, thereby adding a species-specific cost. The surveys identified examples of collective or shared dehulling equipment, a strategy consistent with previous research showing that cooperative investment models reduce capital expenditure in smallholder and diversified cropping systems (Padulosi et al., 2013; Engels, Ebert, 2021). These cases will be further analysed in D5.3 on business models.

For legumes, cost structures vary according to growth habit. Climbing species (e.g., *meat bean*, *lingot bean*) require staking systems, which become essential when mechanical harvesting is employed. Creeping species (e.g., lentils) do not require such infrastructure but may incur higher costs related to weed management or low plant height. Seed cost was also frequently mentioned, although farmers emphasised availability rather than price as the main constraint—consistent with the limited and fragmented seed markets typically associated with neglected and underutilised species. Farmers often mitigate this constraint by retaining part of their harvest for on-farm seed production.

Processors, by contrast, identified several cost drivers arising from the limited and seasonal availability of NUC raw materials. Even for the small- to medium-scale processors targeted by the project—who do not necessarily seek economies of scale—the need to adjust equipment and mobilise labour to handle small, heterogeneous batches leads to higher unit processing costs relative to mainstream crops. Small volume flows impede optimisation of processing lines and increase per-unit labour and energy inputs. These considerations were explicitly discussed during the survey phase through the SMART index linked to processing costs (Table 4).

For both producers and processors, a significant portion of the costs is associated with trial-and-error learning, owing to the limited technical references, best-practice guidelines and extension services available for NUCs. This is one of the main barrier to NUC adoption. However, stakeholders also emphasised that this situation creates opportunities for innovation—particularly for processors, who may differentiate themselves by developing novel transformation techniques, product formulations and market niches.

5. Conclusion

The database structured in DIVINFOOD has made it possible to document numerous and diverse cases of use of NUC genotypes in a variety of agro-pedoclimatic and socio-economic environments, from farms to shops and restaurants. NUCs are globally recognised by their users as catalysts for product diversification, market differentiation, cultural heritage valorisation and sustainability-oriented innovation in agri-food systems. Several scientific articles and practice abstracts have been published based on collected data, or are currently being written.

For some indexes, NUCs benefits can be compared to major crops, as in the example of traditional pea varieties in intercropping with faba bean, which produces grain yields similar to pure stands of modern varieties (e.g., Wallman et al., 2025). For other indexes, there is no benchmark for major crops, then the comparison of benefits between NUCs and major crops is not possible. In any case, the comparison is not as interesting as the complementarity between major and minor crops: DIVINFOOD provides a variety of data that allows this complementarity to be recognised and promoted. The data will be used in several deliverables designed to inspire future users and further support the use of NUCs. The YesWiki tool also offers the possibility of simplified, multilingual versions to be completed by NUC users themselves, which will help to compensate for the lack of data on these species and varieties and strengthen the long-term impact of the project.

Finally, the DIVINFOOD database is the first large-scale use of the open source YesWiki tool as a relational database support, which will serve as an example for future uses.

6. References

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7. Appendixes

7.1 Appendix 1. List of the 240 fields of the GxE database

Various links can exist between the 4 tables for entries (Conceptual data model).

- 1 grower can grow 1 to several (n) batch of agricultural product(s)
- 1 processor can process 1 to several (n) processed product(s)
- 1 seller can sell 1 to several (n) food product(s)

Agricultural product:

- NUC Genotype:

- 3. NUC name *
- 4. Number of species cultivated this year in the growing unit (in average)
- 5. Number of NUC cultivated varieties in field
- 4. NUC cultivar name
- 5. Cultivar type
- 5a. Other cultivar type
- 6. Registered in the country's official seed catalogue
- 7. Seed type
- 7a. Other seed type
- 8. Seed source
- 8a. Other seed source

- Biophysical environment:

- 9. Soil composition
- 10. Soil pH where the NUC is cultivated
- 11. Soil fertility where the NUC is cultivated
- 12. Topography area where the NUC is cultivated
- 13. Altitude where the NUC is cultivated
- 14. Specific climate conditions of the year

- Management practices:

- 15. NUC Batch surface
- 16. Cropping system applied on the NUC batch
- 16a. If mixed crops, other species mixed with the NUC
- 16b. If agroforestry, other species mixed with the NUC
- 17. Previous crops (3 years) before NUC implantation (crop n-1, crop n-2, crop n-3)
- 18. Inputs used to grow the NUC
- 18a. Other input(s)
- 19. Soil management : Type of tillage
- 20. Other practices in relation to agroecology used to cultivate the NUC batch
- 20a. Specify another practice
- 21. NUC - Sowing density
- 22. Sowing date of the NUC

- 23. Harvest date if the NUC
- 24. Picture(s) of agricultural product
- 25. Yield of the NUC batch
- 26. Sanitary quality of the NUC agricultural product batch
- 27. Nutritional quality of the NUC agricultural product batch
- 28. Description - Lab analyses on the quality of the NUC agricultural product batch
- 28a. Document - Lab analyses on the quality of the NUC agricultural product batch
- 29. Grower name (for the pre-processing step) *
- 30. Pre-Processing technique
- 30a. Other pre-processing technique
- 31. Efficiency rate (%)
- 32. Specific(s) condition(s) for pre-processing
- 33. Description - Lab analyses on the pre-processed or agricultural product
- 33a. Document - Lab analyses on the pre-processed or agricultural product
- 34. Picture(s) of pre-processed product issued from the NUC batch

- Marketing Channels:

- 35. Description NUC agricultural product sold
- 36. Stakeholder - First buyer name
- 37. Volume NUC agricultural product sold
- 38. Price NUC agricultural product sold
- 39. Specification imposed to the grower by the processor
- 40. Type of formal contract with the grower by the buyer
- 40a. Contract with other commitment
- 40b. If no contract, type of relation with the grower by the buyer
- 40i. If formal contract with the buyer, duration
- 40i.a. Other contract duration
- 41. Date relationship established / number of years
- 42. Mode of supply delivery
- 42a. Other mode of supply delivery
- 43. Location of the buyer
- 44. Filter : Second buyer for the same NUC Agricultural product batch
- 44i. Filter : Third buyer for the same NUC Agricultural product batch

- Benefits:

- 45. Non-financial benefits for the grower to pre-process the NUC
- 46. Other benefits
- 46a. Document - Other benefits

- Growing and Harvest Costs:

- 47. Equipment used to grow and harvest the NUC
- 48. % use of equipment related to grow and harvest the NUC
- 49. Costs of the equipment(s) (if new)
- 50. Number of working hours devoted to grow and harvest the NUC
- 51. Other direct and indirect costs induced by NUC cultivating and harvesting
- 52. Subsidies to grow the NUC
- 53. Action(s) to reduce costs
- 54. Difficulties encountered in NUC cultivation and harvesting
- 55. Limits/constraints to cultivate and harvest the NUC

- Pre-processing and Storage Costs:

- 56. Equipment used to pre-process and store the NUC if done by the grower
- 57. % use of equipment to pre-process and store the NUC
- 58. Costs of the equipment for pre-processing and storage (if new)
- 59. Number of working hours devoted on pre-processing the NUC
- 60. Costs of NUC pre-processing (if done for the grower by a service provider)
- 61. Other direct and indirect costs induced by the pre-processing of the NUC
- 62. Subsidies to pre-process and store NUC
- 63. Actions to reduce pre-processing costs
- 64. Difficulties encountered in NUC pre-processing and storage
- 65. Limits/constraints to pre-process and store of the NUC

Processed product/dish:

- 1. Processed product / Dish ID *
- 2. Processor name *
- 3. Grower name
- 4. Batch NUC Agricultural Product ID from which the processed product/ dish has been made
- 5. Batch NUC Processed Product/ Dish ID (if the processed product/ dish added above has been made from another processed product)
- 6. NUC name *
- 7. Food product or dish *

- Processed product or dish description:

- 8. Category of agricultural product, primary processing product or processed product made in the unit by the stakeholder
- 8a. Other agricultural product, primary processing product or processed product category made in the unit by the stakeholder
- 9. Category of final processed product made in the unit by the stakeholder
- 9a. Other final processed product category made in the unit by the stakeholder
- 10. Category of final dish made in the processing unit by the stakeholder
- 10a. Other final category of dish made in the processing unit by the stakeholder
- 11. Description of the processed product or dish
- 12. Composition of the processed product or dish
- 13. Description of the recipe

- Processing techniques:

- 14. Processing label
- 14a. Other processing label
- 15. NUC Milling
- 16. Efficiency of milling
- 17. Use of mild-processing technique(s)
- 17a. Other processing technique
- 18. Picture(s) of the processed product or dish step
- 19. By product
- 19a. Other by product

- Quality of the NUC-based processed product or dish:

- 20. Nutritional / Health parameters
- 20a. Document Nutritional / Health parameters
- 21. Organoleptic/ sensorial parameters
- 21a. Document Organoleptic/ sensorial parameters
- 22. Technological quality
- 22a. Document_Technological quality
- 23. Quality evaluation tools
- 23a. Document Quality evaluation tools
- 24. Other benefits of the processed products related to quality
- 24a. Document on other benefits of the processed products related to quality

- Supplier

- 25. Supplier name of the NUC material from which the processed product/dish has been made
- 26. Supply Agricultural Material ID from which the processed product/ dish has been made
- 27. Supply Processed product / Dish ID from which the processed product/dish has been made (if 2 processing steps)
- 28. NUC material type from which the processed product/ dish has been made
- 28a. Other NUC material type from which the processed product/ dish has been made
- 29. Volume of NUC material
- 30. Price supply NUC material
- 31. Specifications imposed/ asked to the supplier of the NUC material
- 32. Type of relationship with the supplier of NUC material
- 32a. If no formal contract, type of relation with the supplier of NUC material
- 32b. If contract with other commitment, type of relation with the supplier of NUC material
- 32i. If formal contract with the supplier, duration
- 32i.a. Other contract duration
- 33. Date of creation of the relationship / number of years
- 34. Mode of supply NUC material
- 34a. Other mode of supply
- 35. Distance with the supplier

- Origin:

- 36. In case of use of NUC primary processing product or processed product, Processing Label applied to it according to the (second) processor
- 36a. Other processing label used according to the processor
- 37. In case of use of NUC primary processing product or processed product, mild processing techniques used in the first step of processing according to the (second) processor
- 37a. Other mild processing techniques used according to the processor
- 38. Cropping system label used to grow the NUC according to the processor
- 38a. If other cropping system label according to the processor
- 39. Practice(s) in relation to agroecology used to cultivate the NUC
- 39a. Specify another practice
- 40. NUC cultivar name (specify if the processor knows it)
- 41. NUC cultivar type (specify if the processor knows it)

- Benefits:

- 42. Benefits for the processor to process the NUC product/ dish (out of financial)
- 42a. Document - Benefits for the processor to process the NUC product/ dish (out of financial)

- Costs:

- 43. Price of service providing for processing NUC material (/kg or ton) if not done by the processor
- 44. Difficulties encountered in processing the NUC Product / Dish
- 45. Equipment used to process the NUC Product / Dish
- 46. % use of equipment related to the processing of the NUC Product / Dish
- 47. Cost of the equipment (if new)
- 48. Number of working hours devoted on processing the NUC Product/ Dish
- 49. Other direct and indirect costs induced by the processing of the NUC Product/ Dish
- 50. Subsidies to process the NUC Product/ Dish
- 51. Action, social organisation reducing the cost to process the NUC Product/ Dish
- 52. Limits/constraints to process the NUC Product/ Dish, comparison with the main legumes/cereals processed in the LL region

Marketed Food Product/ Dish:

- 1. Food Product / Dish ID *
- 2. Seller name *
- 3. Grower name
- 4. Supply Agricultural Product ID
- 5. Processor name
- 6. Supply Processed Product ID
- 7. NUC name *
- 8. Food product or Dish

- Food Product Description:

- 9. Category of the food product
- 10. Picture of the food product
- 11. Description of the product
- 12. Composition of the product
- 13. NUC proportion (%) in the food product

- Food Product Marketing Channel:

- 14. First selling point through which the NUC-based food product is sold
- 14a. Other selling point not described before
- 15. Packaging of the NUC-based product
- 15a. Other packaging of the NUC-based product
- 16. Format/ Weight of the NUC-based product sold in this selling point
- 17. Photo of the NUC-based product packaging_1
- 18. Sale price of the NUC-based product in this selling point (â,¬/kg)
- 19. Volume / weight of the NUC-based product sold (per year)

- 20. Marketing practice(s) applied to the NUC-based food product
- 20a. Other marketing practice not described before
- 21. (If relevant) Type of shelf / category in which the NUC-based product is placed
- 21a. Other type of shelf / category in which the food product is placed
- 22. (If relevant) Placement of the NUC-based product in the shop shelf
- 22a. Other placement of the NUC-based product in the shop shelf
- 23. Communication on the NUC-based product
- 23a. Other communication on the NUC-based product
- 24. Media on or through which the information is provided
- 24a. Other media
- 25. Filter : Second selling point (for the same food product)
- 25i. Filter third selling point (for the same food product)

- Dish Description:

- 26. Category of the dish
- 27. Picture of the dish
- 28. Description of the dish (name and recipe)
- 29. Composition of the dish

- Dish Marketing Channel:

- 30. Selling point through which the dish is sold
- 30a. Other selling point through which the dish is sold
- 31. Marketing practice applied to the dish
- 31a. Other marketing practice not described before
- 32. Sale price of the dish
- 33. Communication about the origin of the NUC-based processed product or NUC agricultural product used in the dish
- 33a. Other communication about the origin of the NUC-based processed product or NUC agricultural product used in the dish
- 34. Media on or through which the information is provided
- 34a. Other media
- 35. Volume/weight of the NUC product used to make the dish in this selling point (per year)
- 36. Volume of the dish sold in this selling point (per day/ month/ year)
- 37. Filter second selling Point (for the same dish)
- 37i. Filter third selling point (for the same dish)

- Supplier (processor and/ or grower):

- 38. Location of the supplier
- 39. Supply price of NUC agricultural or processed product
- 40. Weight supply NUC agricultural or processed product bought to the supplier
- 41. Specifications imposed to the supplier of the NUC agricultural or processed product by the seller
- 42. Type of relationship with the supplier of NUC agricultural or processed product
- 42a. If no formal contract, type of relation with the supplier of the NUC agricultural or processed product
- 42b. If other contract, type of commitment with the supplier of the food product

- 42i. If formal contract with the supplier, duration
- 42i.a. Other contract duration
- 43. Date of creation of the relation / number of years
- 44. Mode of supply
- 44a. Other mode of supply

- Origin:

- 45. Mild-processing techniques/ step applied on the NUC based dish according to the seller
- 45a. Other mild-processing techniques/ step applied on the NUC based dish according to the seller
- 46. Processing system label according to the seller
- 46a. Other Processing system label according to the seller
- 46a. Other processing method/steps
- 47. Mild-processing techniques/ step applied on the NUC processed product according to the seller
- 47a. Other mild-processing techniques/ step applied on the NUC processed product according to the seller
- 48. Growing system label according to the seller
- 48a. Other growing system label according to the seller
- 49. Other practice(s) in relation to agroecology used to cultivate the NUC according to the seller
- 49a. Other agroecological practice according to the seller
- 50. NUC cultivar name according to the seller
- 51. NUC Cultivar type according to the seller

- Benefits:

- 52. Economic benefits to sell the NUC food product / dish for the seller and evaluation methods
- 53. Other benefits for the seller
- 54. Benefits for the consumers and evaluation methods
- 55. Others benefits

- Costs:

- 56. Others direct and indirect costs induced by the sale of the NUC food product/ dish (out of supply costs)
- 57. Subsidies to sell NUC-based product/ dish
- 58. Actions, social organisation, reducing the costs to sell the NUC food product/ dish
- 59. Limits/constraints to sell the NUC-based food product/ dish

7.2 Appendix 2. Classification of verbatims in the SMART indexes

Example for the WP3

SMART Indexes	Assessment method	data type	Bean Lyon	Bean-Cast	Cer-Occ EINKORN
NUC yield	Measurement comparing different crops and/or varieties	quantitative and qualitative	10. In terms of yield, last year Meat bean's yield (25kg/70m ²) was comparable to other beans yield.	213. 2t/ha : Hidalgo : Good but requires treatments.	288. Einkorn yield : 1.6t/ha
			17. 1.5kg in total, so 0.5kg/m ²	266. A long path has been done to manage technically the crop. Now the problem is the yield that is not competitive with the beans grown in other regions of France.	297. So, this year, with the weather we've had, our wheat yields are not good at all (1.5t/ha). But on the other hand, we had the same yield of einkorn as usual (1.2t/ha).
			20. 13.5kg harvested. Vigorous and healthy variety, requiring little intervention. The fact that it is a climbing bean is not an issue because the grower has fixed trellising structures, so there is no additional work time required for staking		310. Yield - IGP Haute Provence - Density : 180kg/ha, yield 480kg/ha, organic.
			21. Very good taste - aesthetic plant and grains - easy to grow (no need to intervene after germination) - interest in local variety valorisation. Yield = 0.7kg/m ²		311. Yield - IGP Haute Provence - 2ha, 1,5t/ha, organic

			25. 380g/m ² : Good quality even if many spots on the grains.		312. Yield - IGP Haute Provence - 2ha, density: 180t/ha, yield 1t/ha, organic
			119. High yield loss because of humidity		313. Yield - Mix Audois - 2ha, 140-160kg/ha, 0,8t/ha.
			154. In comparison with other beans they have tried: 'Coco bean' was sold with the pod, 'Big Borloto' has big red pods so it's easier to harvest. In terms of yield, last year, Meat bean's yield (25kg/70m ²) was comparable to other beans yield.		314. Yield - IGP de Haute deProvence - 80kg/ha. 1.1t/ha

